

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The influence of service quality on outpatient satisfaction at the general polyclinic of the regional general hospital Kendari city 2024

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2025, 26(01), 1501-1515

Publication history: Received on 01 March 2025; revised on 08 April 2025; accepted on 12 April 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2025.26.1.1205>

Abstract

Introduction: Factors that cause low quality of service in hospitals include: physical evidence, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, service performance in health services.

Research objective: To determine the influence of service quality dimensions from the aspects of physical evidence, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and service performance on outpatient satisfaction at the general polyclinic of RSUD Kendari City in 2024.

Method: This research is a quantitative study with a cross-sectional study approach. The data collection technique used accidental sampling and was calculated using Slovin's formula. The research sample consisted of 349 respondents. Data collection techniques utilized questionnaires with a Likert scale. Data analysis techniques included univariate, bivariate, and multivariate analyses using SPSS 2024 Version 29.0. The Chi-square test was conducted on service quality variables and satisfaction variables with a confidence level of 95% ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Results: The results of the study obtained that the results of statistical tests with logistic regression obtained that all independent variables including physical evidence, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, service performance are related to the quality of health services at the General Polyclinic of Kendari City Hospital. Suggestions should be that the management of Kendari City Hospital continues to improve health services periodically in order to create optimal service quality.

Conclusion There is an influence of the quality of services on the satisfaction of outpatients at the General Polyclinic of the Regional General Hospital Kendari.

Keywords: Service Quality; Patient Satisfaction; Outpatient Care; Public Hospital

1. Introduction

Hospitals are healthcare facilities established with the primary aim of providing medical care and medical diagnostic services, as well as medical rehabilitation efforts to meet patient needs. The recovery of patients under treatment is one of the primary objectives of patient care in hospitals. Hospitals, as one of the healthcare service facilities, also serve as referral destinations for lowerlevel healthcare services, private medical practices, and other hospitals. Therefore, as a primary referral destination for healthcare services, hospitals need to maintain the quality of their services to meet the needs of the public. Healthcare services are continually demanded by service users in the healthcare sector to improve and, ultimately, the organization's goal of delivering excellent and quality services can be realized. The quality of health services is a measuring tool used to assess the fulfillment of patient needs and expectations in receiving health services

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in hospitals [1]. Health services are all efforts carried out individually or collectively in an organization to maintain and improve health, prevent and cure disease and restore the health of individuals, families, groups or communities [2] [3]. One of the main requirements for health services is quality, which refers to the level of perfection of the health services provided, which on the one hand can satisfy service users, and on the other hand the procedures for its implementation are in accordance with the code of ethics and standards that have been set [3].

The problem that is often faced in general by hospitals is not being able to provide something that service users really expect. The main factor is because the services provided are of low quality so that they have not been able to produce the services expected by patients. Patient satisfaction as service users is one indicator in assessing the quality of service in hospitals. High satisfaction will indicate the success of the hospital in providing quality health services [4]. The quality of hospital services has two components, namely compliance with established quality standards and compliance with customer satisfaction. Hospitals must provide services that focus on customer satisfaction. Improving the quality of health services can be started by evaluating each element that plays a role in shaping patient satisfaction [5].

Service quality can be measured through several instruments. These instruments include tangibles: appearance of physical facilities, equipment, personnel and communication materials; reliability: the ability to perform promised services reliably and accurately; responsiveness: willingness to help customers and provide prompt service; assurance: employees' knowledge and courtesy and their ability to inspire trust and confidence; empathy: the caring, individualized attention a company gives to customers. In improving service quality, it is necessary to pay attention to one indicator, namely patient satisfaction.

Patient satisfaction can reflect the quality of health services. The more perfect patient satisfaction, the better the quality of health services [6]. This study focused on the types of outpatient services at the general polyclinic of Kendari City Hospital 2024. The polyclinic at Kendari City Hospital 2024 consists of dental, neurology, heart, physiotherapy, nutrition, general surgery, vascular surgery, orthopedics, THT, lung, internal medicine, pediatrics, skin and genitals, occupational therapy, eye, obgyn, general, mental health, urology, endodontics, pediatric dentistry, and VCT.

The number of outpatient recapitulations in each clinic is for the year 2022, namely the dental clinic 245 patients, the neurology clinic 346 patients, heart 178 patients, physiotherapy clinic 0 patients, general surgery clinic 231 patients, vascular surgery 16 patients, orthopedic clinic 158 patients, ear nose throat clinic 596 patients, lung 234 patients, internal medicine clinic 741 patients, pediatric clinic 736 patients, skin and sex clinic 421 patients, occupational therapy 46 patients, eyes 391 patients, ob-gyn 413 patients, general clinic 245 patients. In 2023, the dental clinic had 1156 patients, the neurosurgery clinic had 1519 patients, the cardiac clinic had 1951 patients, the physiotherapy clinic had 966 patients, the general surgery clinic had 209 patients, the vascular surgery clinic had 59 patients, the orthopedic clinic had 846 patients, the ENT clinic had 799 patients, the pulmonary clinic had 580 patients, the internal medicine clinic had 2314 patients, the pediatric clinic had 918 patients, the skin and genital clinic had 886 patients, the occupational therapy clinic had 925 patients, the eye clinic had 1122 patients, the ob-gyn clinic had 320 patients, the general clinic had 6181 patients. In 2024, the dental clinic 1056 patients, neurology clinic 1219 patients, cardiac clinic 1151 patients, physiotherapy clinic 666 patients, general surgery clinic 129 patients, vascular surgery clinic 34 patients, orthopedic clinic 467 patients, ENT clinic 799 patients, pulmonary clinic 300 patients, internal medicine 2314 patients, pediatric clinic 718 patients, skin and sex clinic 586 patients, occupational therapy clinic 925 patients, eye 1122 patients, ob-gyn clinic 220 patients, general clinic 2756 patients [7].

The data on patient visits obtained from the Kendari City Regional General Hospital in the general polyclinic service unit each year in the January - December timeframe each year is that in 2022 there were 4997 outpatients, in 2023 there were 6181 outpatients and in 2024 there were 2756 outpatients. Statistically the last 3 years show fluctuations in the number of outpatients in each year. The trend in the number of patients in the last 3 years indicates a less than optimal quality of service. This is also reflected in the Patient Satisfaction Index at the Kendari City Regional General Hospital in 2021 of 85%, in 2022 of 83%, in 2023 of 87.88% [7].

This achievement of the Patient Satisfaction Index is much lower than the minimum set by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia for patient satisfaction which is above 95% [8]. Kendari City Regional General Hospital in improving the quality of patient health services sets the main indicator, namely the waiting time for outpatients to get health services starting from the patient registering until being served by a doctor with a waiting time ≤ 60 minutes. The outpatient waiting time target set is $\geq 80\%$ of the total patient visits at the Kendari City Regional General Hospital. Data obtained in 2022 the highest outpatient waiting time was 60.38%. Data obtained in 2023 the highest outpatient waiting time was 58.42%. Data obtained in 2024 the highest outpatient waiting time was 66.68% [7]. Data for the last 3 years shows that the target waiting time for outpatients to get services is not achieved every year. This indicates a

problem in the aspect of reliability, namely the ability to provide the promised service immediately, accurately and satisfactorily.

In 2024 the Kendari City Regional General Hospital through the Southeast Sulawesi Hospital Supervisory Board (BPRS) followed up on the results of a hearing conducted by Commission III of the Kendari City DPRD. The problem discussed was the existence of complaints from the public or patients regarding poor services at the Kendari City Regional General Hospital (RSUD), including patients having to wait for hours to see a doctor, health workers directing interns to take action without being accompanied, there are health workers who bring their children while working so that they are less focused on their work and health workers do not show respect to patients or patients' families. This indicates a problem in the aspect of empathy. From the information provided, it appears that there are specific difficulties in improving the quality standards of health services at the Kendari City Regional General Hospital. Therefore, this study was conducted to analyze the quality of health services at Kendari City Regional General Hospital and its impact on patient satisfaction, so as to provide recommendations for relevant improvements.

2. Methods

This type of research is quantitative analytic with a cross-sectional design. This research was conducted in January until February 2024. The location of this research is the General Polyclinic of the regional general hospital kendari city 2024. The population of this study were all patients who had visited and used the Outpatient General Polyclinic Outpatient services at Kendari City Hospital from January to December 2024, totaling 2756 visitors. Then, the number of samples needed is 349 people.

Health service quality is measured based on five dimensions tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, service performance and patient satisfaction. This research data analysis uses univariate, bivariate, and multivariate analysis. Univariate analysis with descriptive in the form of frequency distribution and percentage. Bivariate analysis with chi-square test to analyze the quality of health services and the satisfaction of dental clinic patients at regional general hospital kendari city. Multivariate analysis with logistic regression test to identify the influence between more than one independent variable and one dependent variable. Data processing in this study used computer software in the form of SPSS version 25.0.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Respondent Characteristics

Based on the data in table 1, it can be seen that the characteristics of respondents based on gender in the Outpatient General Polyclinic service of Kendari City Hospital are dominated by men with 201 respondents (58%). From the characteristics of respondents based on age, the majority of respondents aged 41-55 years, namely 138 respondents (40%), in terms of the latest education the majority of respondents have a high school background with a total of 155 respondents (44%), while for the frequency of visits the majority of respondents have visited more than 2 times at the Kendari City Hospital Outpatient General Polyclinic service, namely 212 respondents (61%).

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents Based on Respondent Characteristics at the General Polyclinic Outpatient services at Kendari City Hospital in 2024

No	Respondent Characteristics		Number (n)	Percent (%)	Total
1.	Gender	Man	201	58	100
		Woman	148	42	
2.	Age	17-30 Years old	99	28	100
		31-40 Years old	112	32	
		41-55 Years old	138	40	
3.	Education	Primary School	39	11	100
		Junior high school	75	21	
		Senior high school	155	44	

		PT	80	23	
4.	Frequency of visits	2 times	137	39	100
		> 2 times	212	61	

Source: Primary Data, 2024

3.2. Bivariate Analysis

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Table 2 Relationship between Physical Evidence (Tangible) and Patient Satisfaction at the General Polyclinic Outpatient services at Kendari City Hospital in 2024.

Physical Evidence	Patient Satisfaction				Amount		Pvalue
	Less Satisfied		Satisfied		n	(%)	
	N	(%)	N	(%)			
Good	35	12.2	252	87.8	287	100	0.000
Not enough	11	17.7	51	82.3	62	100	
Total	46	13.2	303	86.8	349	100	

Source: Processed primary data, 2024

Based on Table 2. Shows that of the 287 respondents (100) who have good physical evidence, there are more satisfied patients, namely 252 (87.8%) compared to unsatisfied patients, namely 35 (12.2%). Meanwhile, of the 62 respondents (100%) who had less physical evidence, there were more satisfied patients, namely 51 (82.3%) compared to unsatisfied patients, namely 11 (17.7%).

Based on the Chi-Square test analysis, there is one frequency cell (25%) more than 20% of the data does not match the expected value using the 2x2 table, so an alternative test that can be used if the Chi-Square test results do not meet the requirements is the Fisher Exact test. The Fisher Exact test results obtained a p value = 0.000 ($p > 0.05$) means H_0 is rejected. This shows that there is an influence between physical evidence and patient satisfaction at the General Polyclinic of Kendari City Hospital.

In line with the research conducted by (Burhanuddin, 2016) on the Relationship between Health Service Quality and Patient Satisfaction of Syekh Yusuf Gowa Hospital, the results of the study showed that there was a relationship between tangible, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy with the significance of each dimension being 0.000. The conclusion of this study is that there is a significant relationship between the five dimensions of service quality [9].

The results of this study are in line with the results of the study (Pratama & Harma, 2024) which states that there is a relationship between patient satisfaction with health services and physical evidence [10]. Also supported by the results of the study (Pangerapan, et al., 2018) showing that patient satisfaction in the Polyclinic increases with physical evidence in the hospital [11].

The quality of health services is the degree of perfection of health services that is in accordance with professional standards and service standards by using the potential resources available in the hospital in a reasonable, efficient and effective manner and is provided in a safe and satisfactory manner in terms of norms, legal ethics and cultural ethics by taking into account the limitations and capabilities of the government and consumer society [12]. Health services are a place used to provide health services with an approach of improving health (promotive), preventing disease (preventive), curing disease (curative), and restoring health (rehabilitative) which is carried out in a comprehensive, integrated and sustainable manner [13].

Physical evidence of a service can be seen from the competence of health workers. This competence includes the knowledge, skills, and attitudes possessed by health workers in providing services. Good competence from health workers will create patient trust in the quality of services provided. The facilities and infrastructure available at health

service facilities can facilitate the implementation of good services. The dimension of physical evidence is a real (physical) form and form of service that will later be obtained by patients. The dimension of physical evidence shows the hospital's ability to show its existence to patients such as a good building appearance, comfortable rooms, neatly dressed health workers, neat service area arrangement, complete waiting room facilities, and service flows that make it easier for patients [14].

In general, patients who stated that physical evidence was good were more numerous than patients who stated that physical evidence was lacking. This shows that the higher the physical evidence, the higher the level of patient satisfaction with the health services provided by medical personnel. Conversely, the lower the physical evidence, the lower the level of patient satisfaction with health services. This occurs because physical evidence, such as adequate building conditions, easily accessible polyclinic locations, waiting rooms with comfortable air circulation and sufficient seating, good medical equipment, and professionalism of medical personnel, can provide a better perception of the quality of service received by patients. When patients experience good physical service, they tend to feel appreciated and cared for, which can increase patient satisfaction levels.

On the other hand, if the physical evidence received by the patient is inadequate, such as less clean and comfortable toilet facilities, less friendly staff and unprofessional interactions from medical staff, no directions to the pharmacy so that patients feel dissatisfied or even disappointed with the services provided. This can affect the perception of the quality of health services as a whole. Therefore, good physical evidence plays a very important role in shaping positive patient experiences and increasing their satisfaction with health services.

Patient demands for good quality health services are seen from the dimensions of physical evidence such as the condition of the polyclinic building, the layout of the polyclinic location is very good and clean, the polyclinic waiting room has a clean toilet, the attitude of the officers when patients seek treatment, clear and informative signs and directions for patients to the pharmacy, lighting in the polyclinic waiting room is sufficient, air circulation in the polyclinic waiting room is sufficient, the number of seats in the polyclinic waiting room is sufficient, facilities that make patients comfortable such as air conditioning, fans, and televisions are available in the polyclinic waiting room, medical equipment owned by the polyclinic is adequate.

The aspects that contribute most to patient satisfaction include the layout of the Polyclinic location which is good and clean so that patients feel more comfortable and safe. A clean environment creates an impression of professionalism and attention to service quality. Air circulation in the Polyclinic waiting room is sufficient. With sufficient air circulation, the air in the waiting room can move and replace contaminated air with fresh air. This is important for patients to prevent the spread of viruses, bacteria or other pathogens that can be transferred between patients, especially in waiting rooms that are often filled with many people. Sufficient number of seats in the Polyclinic waiting room where with enough seats, patients can sit comfortably and reduce physical fatigue while waiting. Facilities that make patients comfortable such as air conditioning, fans, and televisions available in the Polyclinic waiting room. With these facilities patients will feel more relaxed and comfortable patients who are waiting for the queue and adequate medical equipment owned by the polyclinic so as to increase patient confidence in the medical practices applied.

While aspects that contribute less to patient satisfaction include the polyclinic waiting room having an unclean toilet, so that patients feel uncomfortable, especially when they have to wait for a long time for treatment. Therefore, it is important for the polyclinic to ensure that staff are not only professional in providing medical care, but also friendly, empathetic, and communicative to create a supportive environment for patients. Signs and patient directions to the pharmacy that are not clear and informative often confuse patients who want to go to the pharmacy and ask questions to other patients, causing discomfort and increasing tension among patients.

The results of this study indicate that the physical evidence of outpatient General Polyclinic services has generally met patient expectations. Where patients want a good building, affordable location, clean room, good air circulation in the waiting room and complete equipment, availability of seating in the waiting room, and a comfortable waiting room. However, there are some that need to be improved by the polyclinic such as being friendly to patients, continuous cleaning of toilets and directions in each room, especially directions to the pharmacy. Overall, each of these aspects contributes to patients' confidence in the healthcare system and increases their satisfaction with the services provided. When medical personnel demonstrate skill, accuracy and attention to patient needs, it creates a positive experience and increases the overall level of patient satisfaction.

Table 3 Relationship between Reliability and Patient Satisfaction at the General Polyclinic Outpatient services at Kendari City Hospital in 2024.

Reliability	Patient Satisfaction				Amount		Pvalue
	Less Satisfied		Satisfied		n	100	
	N	(%)	N	(%)			
Good	11	6.8	150	93.2	161	100	0.001
Not enough	35	18.6	153	81.4	188	100	
Total	46	13.2	303	86.8	349	100	

Source: Processed primary data, 2024.

Based on Table 3. Shows that of the 161 respondents (100) who had good physical evidence, there were more satisfied patients, namely 150 (93.2%) compared to 11 (6.8%) dissatisfied patients. Meanwhile, of the 188 respondents (100%) who had less physical evidence, there were more satisfied patients, namely 153 (81.4%) compared to unsatisfied patients, namely 35 (18.6%).

Based on Table 3. Shows the p-value of the Physical Evidence $0.000 < 0.05$ so it can be concluded that there is a relationship between physical evidence at health services and Outpatient Satisfaction at the General Polyclinic Outpatient services at Kendari City Hospital.

In line with the results of research by (Idrus, et al., 2025) shows that the five dimensions of service quality such as tangible (physical evidence), reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy have an influence between the five service quality variables on satisfaction. Based on the results of the study, analysis and discussion it can be concluded that the results of the Chi-Square test obtained that the p-value was $0.000 < 0.005$. The conclusion of this study is that the quality of health services affects patient satisfaction at the Mataram University Hospital [15].

This is also in line with the results of the study (Irianto, et al., 2020) which states that there is a significant relationship between service quality and outpatient satisfaction, namely in the reliability dimension, the quality of health services where medical personnel in providing explanations of drug use is stated as good because according to respondents, officers always provide brief and clear information when taking drugs. While the statement of the waiting time to get a prescription and medicine is stated as not good, this is supported by complaints from several patients when redeeming medicine sometimes have to wait a long time to get medicine. In addition, the distance to the pharmacy is far so that patients need a long time to get medicine [16].

Reliability in the quality of service provided by officers is assessed from the knowledge and skills they have, the mastery of officers in carrying out tasks according to their fields and the accuracy and precision of the health services provided. In addition, the level of satisfaction in the Reliability dimension can also be assessed from the competence of officers when providing health services [17].

In the reliability dimension, the quality of outpatient General Polyclinic services at Kendari City Hospital was stated to be lacking by 81.4%. Respondents' assessments that assessed the waiting time in preparing and submitting prescriptions and medical personnel not arriving on time were also considered less than satisfactory. Meanwhile, 93.2% of respondents assessed it as good from aspects such as uncomplicated administration, officers willing to explain the information on the drugs needed, caring about the patient's condition, trying to provide a faster response to patients, and officers providing explanations related to patient needs. Respondents who were satisfied with the reliability dimension reflected that General Polyclinic officers were skilled in providing information related to treatment to patients.

In general, patients who stated good responsiveness were more numerous than patients who stated that there was insufficient physical evidence. This shows that the higher the responsiveness, the higher the level of patient satisfaction with the health services provided by medical personnel. Conversely, the lower the responsiveness, the lower the level of patient satisfaction with health services. This occurs because of responsiveness, such as uncomplicated administration, officers are willing to explain the information on the drugs needed, are concerned about the patient's condition, try to provide a faster response to patients, and officers provide explanations related to patient needs.

The most significant contributing aspects to patient satisfaction include the staff being on time in issuing referral letters so that they feel they can continue treatment to the desired hospital. The medicine given by the pharmacist is in accordance with the prescription issued by the doctor so that the patient is safe to use the medicine. The pharmacist explains and gives the medicine to the patient along with the drug usage label so that the patient understands the procedure for using the medicine. Nurses are proficient in using medical equipment so that patients can more quickly find out the initial diagnosis of the disease suffered by the patient. Meanwhile, aspects that contribute less to patient satisfaction include the available medicines are not always available at the pharmacy so that patients often have to buy them at pharmacies outside the Kendari City Hospital polyclinic. The waiting time to get the prescribed medicine is often slow up to 60 minutes, the information signs are inadequate so that patients are often confused about finding a service location and a pharmacy that is located on a different floor from the polyclinic. Medical personnel are less disciplined, especially doctors, where patients often have to wait a long time to get health services.

Table 4 Relationship between Responsiveness and Patient Satisfaction at the General Polyclinic Outpatient services at Kendari City Hospital in 2024.

Responsiveness	Patient Satisfaction				Amount		Pvalue
	Less Satisfied		Satisfied		n	(%)	
	N	(%)	N	(%)			
Good	23	8.1	261	91.9	284	100	0.000
Not enough	23	85.4	42	64.6	65	100	
Total	46	13.2	303	86.8	349	100	

Source: Processed primary data, 2024.

Based on Table 4. Shows that of the 284 respondents (100) who had good physical evidence, there were more satisfied patients, namely 261 (91.9%) compared to unsatisfied patients, namely 23 (8.1%). Meanwhile, of the 65 respondents (100%) who had less physical evidence, there were more satisfied patients, namely 42 (64.6%) compared to unsatisfied patients, namely 23 (85.4%).

Based on Table 4. Shows the p-value of the Physical Evidence $0.000 < 0.05$ so it can be concluded that there is a relationship between physical evidence at health services and Outpatient Satisfaction at the General Polyclinic Outpatient services at Kendari City Hospital.

Responsiveness is the alertness or ability of medical personnel to help, provide responsive and fast services to patients [18]. The dimensions of responsiveness can be assessed through several abilities such as the ability to provide good, skilled, and fast services, the alertness of officers in helping patients, the ability of officers to respond to patient complaints. According to (Parasuraman, et al., 2011), responsiveness is the willingness or desire of employees to help and provide the services needed by consumers [19].

The opinion of researchers from (Netriadi, et al., 2021) states that the ability to help customers and provide services quickly and accurately with clear information delivery. Ignoring and letting customers wait for no apparent reason causes a negative perception of service quality [20].

From the results of the research analysis, it was found that responsiveness with a good score was greater than patients who stated responsiveness with a poor score. This shows that the higher the responsiveness, the higher the level of patient satisfaction with health services. Conversely, the lower the responsiveness, the lower the level of outpatient satisfaction of the General Polyclinic of Kendari City Hospital. This happens because good responsiveness from medical personnel creates a more positive experience for patients. When medical personnel or hospital staff can immediately and effectively respond to the needs, questions, or problems faced by patients, patients feel valued and prioritized. In the context of health services, responsiveness includes several aspects, such as speed in providing services, accuracy in answering patient questions or complaints, and the ability to provide adequate solutions in a timely manner.

The results of the study also showed that some patients wanted a waiting time for taking medication of less than 60 minutes and officers to arrive on time. The most significant aspect of responsiveness that contributed significantly to patient satisfaction included officers providing good and fast responses to patient complaints so that patients felt valued, prioritized, and received appropriate attention. Patient administration services during treatment were not complicated and simple, also creating the impression that the polyclinic or health facility had a well-organized system

and valued patient time. Officers who were willing to help and cared and tried to meet patient needs had a very big impact on patient satisfaction. When medical officers or hospital staff showed empathy and attention to patients, patients felt valued and prioritized. Feeling well cared for by officers creates a more positive relationship between patients and medical personnel, which can increase patient confidence in the care they receive.

The caring and helpful attitude provided by the staff also creates a sense of comfort and reduces anxiety that is often experienced by patients, especially when they are in a vulnerable condition or are experiencing health problems. When staff strive to meet the needs of patients, whether by providing clear information, helping to resolve problems that arise, or ensuring patient comfort during the treatment process, patients feel calmer and more confident that they are getting the attention they deserve. In addition, the caring attitude of the staff also improves the overall patient experience. Patients are not only seeking medical care, but they are also seeking emotional support and attention in dealing with their health conditions.

Aspects of responsiveness that do not contribute to patient satisfaction include health workers who are often not on time so that patients sometimes wait too long and do not get timely service. This habit can make patients feel unappreciated, thus reducing trust in the quality of services provided. In addition, waiting times for taking medication that reach 60 minutes have a negative impact on patient satisfaction. When patients have to wait a long time to get medication, they tend to feel frustrated and disappointed, especially if the waiting time was not anticipated in advance. The length of the waiting time can add to the mental burden of patients who are already anxious or uncomfortable with their health condition. Long waiting times can also cause physical or emotional discomfort, especially for patients in conditions that require rapid treatment, such as patients who are seriously ill or undergoing post-operative care. Delays in getting medication can worsen the patient's condition, which ultimately affects their perception of the quality of medical services provided.

Table 5 Relationship between Guarantee and Patient Satisfaction at the General Polyclinic Outpatient services at Kendari City Hospital in 2024.

Guarantee	Patient Satisfaction				Amount		Pvalue
	Less Satisfied		Satisfied		n	(%)	
	N	(%)	N	(%)			
Good	29	10.4	251	89.6	280	100	0.004
Not enough	17	24.6	52	75.4	69	100	
Total	46	13.2	303	86.8	349	100	

Source: Processed primary data, 2024.

Based on Table 5. Shows the p-value of the Physical Evidence $0.000 < 0.05$ so it can be concluded that there is a relationship between physical evidence at health services and Outpatient Satisfaction at the General Polyclinic Outpatient services at Kendari City Hospital.

Based on Table 5. Shows that of the 280 respondents (100) who have good physical evidence, there are more satisfied patients, namely 251 (89.6%) compared to unsatisfied patients, namely 29 (10.4%). Meanwhile, of the 69 respondents (100%) who had less physical evidence, there were more satisfied patients, namely 52 (75.4%) compared to unsatisfied patients, namely 17 (24.6%).

Assurance relates to the hospital's ability to provide qualified and skilled health workers as promised so that outpatients in the polyclinic have confidence in the treatment process for healing their illnesses. In the assurance dimension, patient confidence in the guarantee of healing and safety due to the services provided, including the knowledge of health workers in providing services [21].

Research conducted by (Noorhidayat, et al., 2019) which states that there is a significant influence of tangible evidence, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy on BPJS patient satisfaction at the Outpatient Service of Ratu Zalecha General Hospital in 2019. In his research that the guarantee given by the officers was good in terms of guaranteeing explanations about examinations/services, easy to understand and comprehend. However, there are still respondents who state that the guarantee is not good because it is still lacking in terms of guaranteeing the environment where the service is located [22].

In line with the results of research conducted by (Dahlan, et al., 2021) that the guarantee variable has a positive and very significant effect on participant satisfaction at the BPJS Health Office of South Konawe Regency, meaning that the better the guarantee, the more significant the participant satisfaction with administrative services at the BPJS Health Office of South Konawe Regency will be [23]. In contrast to the results of research conducted by (Sugiono, 2015) which stated that the dimensions of the guarantee aspect provided by the Health Center on patient satisfaction did not have a very strong and significant effect [24].

In this study, the assurance dimension was assessed based on the accuracy of officers in providing drugs accompanied by labels, officers provide drugs based on Standard Operating Procedures, pharmacists in handing over drugs provide an explanation of how to use them, officers have good knowledge of drugs, information provided by officers is reliable, and the drugs redeemed are guaranteed to be safe. Pharmacists prepare drugs according to the prescription given.

Quality of service is a choice that will affect the satisfaction of patients who will be treated at Kendari City Hospital. Good quality of service will create its own satisfaction for patients. The creation of quality that can provide benefits to harmonious service units and patients. Global progress has a positive impact on health service providers so that quality of service is the main demand for patients. According to [25].

In general, patients who stated good assurance were more numerous than patients who stated poor assurance. This shows that the higher the assurance, the higher the level of patient satisfaction with health services. Conversely, the lower the assurance, the lower the level of patient satisfaction with health services at the General Polyclinic of Kendari City Hospital. This occurs because good assurance provides a sense of security and comfort for patients, both in terms of the safety of using drugs, assurance of getting drugs according to patient needs, and drug packaging guaranteed with labels for drinking rules and other services. When patients feel that they are guaranteed by medical personnel, patients tend to feel more satisfied with the services provided. Good assurance can also create a positive perception of the quality of service received, which in turn increases overall satisfaction.

The most significant contributing aspects to patient satisfaction in the assurance dimension include the packaging of drugs provided by officers accompanied by drug labels so that patients can easily understand how to use the drug, the correct dosage, time of administration, and possible side effects. Clear and informative labels help patients avoid mistakes in drug use, ensure that drugs are consumed in the correct manner, and increase the effectiveness of treatment. In addition, drug labels also provide important information about contraindications, interactions with other drugs, and special warnings that patients need to pay attention to. Good knowledge also allows medical personnel to choose the right drug according to the patient's condition and ensure that the drug therapy given is safe and effective. Meanwhile, aspects that contribute less to patient satisfaction in the assurance aspect include the number of drugs available at the pharmacy is not always available according to the patient's needs so that it can cause delays in treatment or even require patients to look for drugs elsewhere, which can affect patient comfort and satisfaction with health services. The unavailability of the right drugs can also increase patient anxiety, because patients feel less than optimal or hampered. In addition, if the required medication is not available, patients are often forced to use substitute medications that are not as effective or appropriate for the patient's medical condition, which can have a negative impact on treatment outcomes. Therefore, it is important for health facilities to maintain a complete and appropriate supply of medication for patients so that the treatment process can run smoothly and patients get maximum results from the care provided.

Table 6 Relationship between Empathy and Patient Satisfaction at the General Polyclinic Outpatient services at Kendari City Hospital in 2024.

Empathy	Patient Satisfaction				Amount		Pvalue
	Less Satisfied		Satisfied		n	%	
	N	(%)	N	(%)			
Good	29	9.8	266	90.2	295	100	0.000
Not enough	17	31.5	37	68.5	54	100	
Total	46	13.2	303	86.8	349	100	

Source: Processed primary data, 2024.

Based on Table 6. Shows that of the 295 respondents (100) who had good physical evidence, there were more satisfied patients, namely 266 (90.2%) compared to unsatisfied patients, namely 29 (9.8%). Meanwhile, of the 54 respondents

(100%) who had less physical evidence, there were more satisfied patients, namely 37 (68.5%) compared to unsatisfied patients, namely 17 (31.5%).

Based on Table 6. Shows the p-value of the Physical Evidence $0.000 < 0.05$ so it can be concluded that there is a relationship between physical evidence at health services and Outpatient Satisfaction at the General Polyclinic Outpatient services at Kendari City Hospital.

Empathy can be seen from the ability of medical staff to show concern for what patients need, understand what patients feel and need, and be able to establish a good relationship with patients. The care provided by health workers in the form of attention to both patient complaints and complaints from the patient's family without differentiating or seeing their background or social status will affect the level of patient satisfaction [26].

Health services are one of the factors that affect the degree of public health. Quality service in the context of services in health facilities, is providing services to patients and their families according to quality standards to meet their needs and desires, so that they can get satisfaction which can increase the trust of patients and their families [27].

In the empathy dimension, the quality of outpatient health services is stated to be good as many as 90.5% of respondents, seen from an emotional point of view, namely officers pay attention and are polite when providing services, communicate well and can understand what the patient feels. Empathy is important for health workers because by having a sense of concern and being more responsive to patients, it will speed up the patient's recovery time. In line with research conducted by (Andriani, 2017) that patients are very satisfied with the empathy dimension obtained an average percentage score of 88.9% categorized on a Likert scale, namely very satisfied. Based on research data that there is a relationship between service quality and patient satisfaction because service quality is one of the duties and responsibilities of nurses as a component that runs the service. Therefore, nurses must be able to provide services that satisfy every patient who visits. This quality of service must be applied in accordance with the provisions and policies set for all health institutions, because the level of satisfaction is a benchmark of the quality of service of an institution. Every health care worker must have a sense of empathy and a sense of rapid response in providing health services in order to achieve a high level of satisfaction with patients. Therefore, health institutions are very concerned about the quality of service. So that there is a relationship between service quality and patient satisfaction [28].

This study is also in line with research conducted by (Evi, et al., 2022) which states that the level of patient satisfaction at RSUD dr. Soediran Mangun Sumarso Wonogiri in the empathy dimension is in the very satisfied category (89.40%). The highest value is in the indicator of friendly officers when providing services to patients as much as 90.40% in the very satisfied category. Empathy can be seen from the officer's ability to show concern for what the patient needs, understand what the patient feels and needs, and be able to establish a good relationship with the patient. The assessment of the empathy dimension can be seen in the officer's concern in responding to patient and family complaints by not differentiating the patient's background. In addition, officers are also friendly in listening to what the patient's complaints are and patiently explaining in a language that is easily understood by patients and families [29].

The caring and friendly attitude shown by pharmaceutical officers to all patients regardless of religion, ethnicity, and social status makes patients feel comfortable. This will have an impact on the level of patient satisfaction where when the patient feels comfortable with the services provided, it will indirectly cause a sense of wanting to come back again [30]. The empathy dimension in health care plays an important role in improving patient satisfaction because it reflects the ability of health workers to understand the needs, concerns, and conditions of patients personally. Empathy includes individual attention, willingness to listen, and a caring attitude towards the patient's well-being. When health workers demonstrate empathy, patients feel valued and treated as individuals, not just service users. This creates a positive emotional connection, increases trust, and promotes more effective communication between patients and healthcare workers as a result, patients are more satisfied with the care they receive and tend to be more adherent to recommended therapies, which ultimately results in better health outcomes.

The aspect that contributes most to patient satisfaction in the empathy aspect is that medical personnel understand the patient's needs and provide solutions so that patients feel cared for and receive appropriate care according to the patient's condition. With a good understanding of patient needs, medical personnel can provide more personalized and effective treatment, reduce the risk of errors in diagnosis or treatment, and increase patient trust in the services provided. In addition, the ability of medical personnel to provide appropriate solutions can also help patients feel more comfortable and safe during the treatment process. This responsive approach increases patient satisfaction and contributes to better treatment outcomes. Meanwhile, aspects that contribute less to patient satisfaction in the empathy aspect are being friendly and polite when providing services so that patients feel unappreciated, anxious, or even uncomfortable. This attitude can reduce patient trust in the services provided, increase frustration, and worsen patient

conditions in the polyclinic. In addition, unfriendliness and rudeness of officers can create poor communication between patients and medical personnel, which can cause patients to be less open in conveying their complaints or health problems. This can risk inaccurate diagnoses or less than optimal treatment, as well as reducing the level of patient satisfaction with the quality of health services they receive. In the long term, this can also affect the reputation of the hospital.

The results of this study indicate that the empathetic attitude of officers at the General Polyclinic for outpatients has generally met patient expectations. Where patients want medical officers to understand their needs, provide attention, be patient in receiving complaints, provide concern, and not be easily offended and provide solutions to what the patient's problems are. The empathetic attitude shown by medical officers, such as not being easily offended and providing relevant solutions to patient problems, also helps create a better relationship between patients and medical officers. This not only contributes to more effective complaint management, but also increases patient comfort and confidence in undergoing treatment. Thus, an empathetic attitude that is well implemented by medical officers can be a key factor in improving the quality of health services, as well as ensuring that patients feel more cared for and supported during the treatment process.

Table 7 Relationship between Service Performance and Patient Satisfaction at the General Polyclinic Outpatient services at Kendari City Hospital in 2024.

Service Performance	Patient Satisfaction				Amount		Pvalue
	Less Satisfied		Satisfied		n	%	
	N	(%)	N	(%)			
Good	26	9.5	248	90.5	274	100	0.000
Not enough	20	26.7	55	73.3	75	100	
Total	46	13.2	303	86.8	349	100	

Source: Processed primary data, 2024.

Based on Table 7. Shows that of the 274 respondents (100) who had good physical evidence, there were more satisfied patients, namely 248 (90.5%) compared to unsatisfied patients, namely 26 (9.5%). Meanwhile, of the 75 respondents (100%) who had less physical evidence, there were more satisfied patients, namely 55 (73.3%) compared to unsatisfied patients, namely 20 (26.7%). The majority of respondents 90.5% assessed that the service performance dimension was good or the patient was satisfied as seen from the medicine given to the patient according to what was stated in the prescription, the officer provided services quickly and accurately, information and counseling about the drugs provided such as the name of the drug, the amount of the drug, the dosage and the rules for using the drug, special rules, indications, side effects, contraindications, and expiration dates.

Based on Table 7. Shows the p-value of the Physical Evidence 0.000 <0.05 so it can be concluded that there is a relationship between physical evidence at health services and Outpatient Satisfaction at the General Polyclinic Outpatient services at Kendari City Hospital.

Patient satisfaction is a comparison between expectations and the reality that patients feel after getting health services from officers. Patients will feel satisfied if they get health services at least in accordance with their expectations and even more than they expected. The achievement of patient expectations will have an impact on patient satisfaction with the services provided. Good quality health services are health services that are carried out in accordance with applicable standard operating procedures and professional codes of ethics [31].

If service performance variables in health services are considered deficient, the impact can be a decrease in the level of satisfaction of outpatients, even potentially causing health risks. Discrepancies, such as non-prescribed medication, inaccurate medication information, or violations of standardized procedures, can cause patient confusion, distrust, and discomfort. It may also increase the risk of side effects, unwanted drug interactions, or ineffectiveness of therapy, thus hindering treatment outcomes. In the long run, inadequate service can damage the provider's image, decrease patient loyalty, and increase the potential for complaints or lawsuits. Therefore, ensuring service performance to established standards is essential to maintain patient trust and satisfaction [32].

3.3. Multivariate Analysis

This analysis is to see the influence (relationship) between the independent variables on the dependent variable using the logistic regression analysis type so that the independent variable that most dominantly influences the dependent variable is obtained.

Table 8 The Influence of Physical Evidence (Tangible), Reliability, Responsiveness, Guarantee, Empathy and Service Performance on Outpatient Satisfaction at the General Polyclinic Outpatient services at Kendari City Hospital.

Variables	B	S.E	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
Physical Evidence	-1.089	.546	3.982	1	0.046	0.337
Reliability	0.585	.420	4.176	1	0.041	2.359
Responsiveness	1.971	.574	11.777	1	0.001	7.178
Guarantee	1.686	.432	15.237	1	0.001	5.400
Empathy	1.119	.539	4.310	1	0.038	3.061
Service performance	1.684	.422	15.895	1	0.001	5.389

Source: Processed primary data, 2024.

Based on Table 8, after conducting a logistic regression test, it is known that the variables of Physical Evidence, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy and Service Performance have a positive sig value (p-value) and each with a sig value (p-value) <0.05. This means that the six variables interact with each other to influence Patient Satisfaction at the General Polyclinic Outpatient services at Kendari City Hospital. Step furthermore, to determine the magnitude of the influence of the six variables on Patient Satisfaction which is indicated by the wald value, namely:

- On the physical evidence variable (tangible) with a wald value of 3.982, it means that each one unit of physical evidence will have an effect of 3.982 on outpatient satisfaction at the General Polyclinic of Kendari City Hospital.
- On the reliability variable (reliability) with a wald value of 4.176, it means that each one unit of reliability will have an effect of 4.176 on outpatient satisfaction at the General Polyclinic of the Kendari City Hospital.
- On the responsiveness variable with a wald value of 11,777, it means that each one unit of responsiveness will have an effect of 11,777 on outpatient satisfaction at the General Polyclinic of the Kendari City Hospital.
- On the assurance variable with a wald value of 15,237, it means that each one unit of assurance will have an effect of 15,237 on outpatient satisfaction at the General Polyclinic of the Kendari City Hospital.
- On the empathy variable with a wald value of 4,310, it means that each one unit of empathy will have an effect of 4,310 on outpatient satisfaction at the General Polyclinic of the Kendari City Hospital.
- In the service performance variable (service performance) with a wald value of 15,895, it means that each one unit of service performance will have an effect of 15,895 on outpatient satisfaction at the General Polyclinic of the Kendari City Hospital.

So, it can be concluded that the most dominant variable affecting patient satisfaction is service performance with a wald value of 15.895, each one unit of service performance has the opportunity to have an influence of 15.895 on outpatient satisfaction at the General Polyclinic of Kendari City Hospital. Based on the results of statistical tests as well as the results of the data analysis above, it will be a guide for hospital management to be able to interpret, predict, and determine what programs are relevant to improving service performance at the General Polyclinic of Kendari City Hospital.

The responsiveness variable can be very influential compared to other variables in the context of patient satisfaction because it is directly related to the patient's experience during the service process. Patients tend to feel more satisfied when their needs or complaints are addressed quickly and effectively. In healthcare, this includes aspects such as speed of service delivery, the ability to answer patient questions in a clear and timely manner, and responsiveness to problems or concerns that arise during treatment. Speed of service, minimal waiting time, and alertness in responding to patient requests or complaints can increase patients' feelings of being valued and prioritized [3].

Responsiveness also strengthens patients' trust in the quality of service provided. Patients who feel served quickly and responsively will have a positive perception of the efficiency and professionalism of the health facility, which will increase their loyalty. Therefore, the responsiveness variable can be more influential than other variables because of its direct impact on patient experience regarding their comfort and satisfaction in receiving services [6].

Patient satisfaction is an integral part and quality assurance activities in health services, meaning that patient satisfaction must be an activity that cannot be separated from the quality of health services. Health services to patients are carried out directly with full responsibility [33].

Patient satisfaction with the services provided can also be assessed from the speed of service provided by the officer. The faster the service is provided, the higher the level of satisfaction felt by the patient. Dissatisfaction that arises in patients will greatly affect the quality of health care facilities such as hospitals. It is necessary to measure the level of patient satisfaction by assessing the quality of service expected with the service obtained so that it can determine the magnitude of the existing gap [34].

4. Conclusion

There is an influence of the quality of health services based on the dimensions of Physical Evidence, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy, and Service Performance on the satisfaction of outpatients at the General Polyclinic of the Kendari City Regional General Hospital. The dimension that has the most significant influence on the satisfaction of outpatients at the General Polyclinic of the Kendari City Regional General Hospital is Responsiveness.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors have no conflict of interest in this research.

Statement of ethical approval

This research has obtained a permit or recommendation from the Health Study Ethics Committee (KEPK) of the Regional Management of the Indonesian Public Health Experts Association (IAKMI) of Southeast Sulawesi Province with Number 37/KEPK-IAKMI/III/2025.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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